

ISSUES OF ATTRACTING BORROWINGS FROM THE CAPITAL MARKET TO THE LOCAL BUDGET

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of characteristics of debt instruments raised by local governments from the capital market. In addition, the article analyzes advantages and disadvantages of debt financing are analyzed. Herewith the municipal budget deficit of municipal bonds has been studied as an essential tool in the independent solution of problems related to subsidies received from the higher budget.

Key words: debt financing, bank loan, municipal bonds, interest rate, yield, maturity, risk.

1. Introduction

One of the ways for local governments to raise borrowings from the capital market is to issue municipal debt securities. Comprehensive development of the bond debt system enables to independently solve the problems related to local budget deficits and subsidies received from the higher budget, in particular, to finance projects for further development and modernization of regional production, engineering, communication and social infrastructure. Development and efficiency of the capital market includes a number of factors, such as statutory framework, tax environment, investor’s behavior, economic situation of the country, market liquidity, data openness and transparency, education and available knowledge (Pociusa et al., 2014).

Inadequate base of local budget revenue and growing need to finance expenditure commitments, in turn, result in the increase in the demand of local

governments to borrow funds from the capital market. All debt instruments of regional authorities can be presented in the form of independently attracted resources, such as loans and bonds.

2. Literature review

Municipal bonds are issued by municipalities and local governments basically to finance various social projects, including school construction, road repairs, water supply and sewerage overhaul. In order to reduce the expenses on borrowings of the local government and self-governing authorities, the revenue from municipal bonds is exempted from federal and, in many cases, income taxes imposed by the state. These tax incentives will create tax expenditures for the federal and state budgets, which are forecasted to cost the amount of 500.0 billion USD for the federal government. It is supposed to demonstrate an upward trend in the next decade, and high-income individuals can enjoy using this tax incentive. It is no coincidence, therefore, that the tax advantage of municipal bonds has become the subject of political arguments.

The IMF (1997) considered introduction of tax incentives on interest income on municipal bonds as a common measure to encourage an investor's interest in regional securities and as a way to subsidize local government spending. In the opinion of Murynov (2000), in the process of introducing preferential taxation of income on municipal securities, it is required to elaborate a more detailed mechanism for determining the value of such income in tax legislation. This is necessary to distinguish between the investor's gross income on long-term coupon bonds and income from the growth of the market value of bonds (capital growth). Murynov (2000) considered such issues as that relative losses of local authorities in the introduction of a tax on municipal securities are directly proportional to the

tax rates; prolongation of the circulation period of securities issued by federal entities and local governments can result in the increase in losses from relative taxation under other equal conditions. He thinks, that the higher the market return on equilibrium and the risk value of investments is, the greater the loss of subfederal securities issuers is observed. In reliance upon the findings of the research, it can be concluded that the current system of taxation of securities of federal entities and municipalities in Russia worsens the conditions for attracting loan resources, hinders the development of the subfederal securities market and thus solves many urgent problems of local finance. Herewith, the current taxation system provides favorable conditions for short-term loans over long-term debt instruments, i.e. indirect incentives for securities issued to finance local budget deficits, rather than to solve regional development problems. This fact inevitably causes a debt crisis in the country (Murynov, 2000).

From the point of view of Novikov (1997), the USA experience in the municipal securities market, in which the securities of more developed* states and municipalities are circulating, is significant in the application of tax incentives to interest income. Interest income on municipal securities is not subject to federal income tax and is also exempted from income taxes of the states and municipalities in which they are issued. In addition, in some states, interest income on municipal securities issued in other states is not subject to taxation. Meanwhile, private activity bonds, which are municipal bonds by nature, have been issued to attract private investment in projects for certain social benefits. Kinsellagh (2019) supposes that municipal bonds are valued on a scale used to assess the risk of corporate debt obligations as well. On the contrary, the majority of low-ranking

* In 1996, the capitalization of the municipal bond market in the USA reached 1.6 trillion USD.

state or local governments with poor financial condition often have higher returns. The advantage of municipal bonds and their attractiveness is that the debt is reliably and fully secured by the issuer. Local governments that sell their debts to investors are entitled to tax if additional income is required to pay semi-annual interest on the bonds, and bonds issued by private corporations do not have such tax capability. Moreover, Mishkin and Eakins (2012) have noted that interest income on municipal bonds in the United States is exempted from federal income tax, which makes an impact on the demand for municipal bonds and the expected increase in income.

3. Research methodology

The findings of research by economists on essential aspects of municipal bonds have been used in this paper. Such research methods as scientific abstraction, induction and deduction, methods of analysis have been widely applied in the research.

4. Analysis and Results

The credit risk of the bonds arises from the inability or unwillingness of the issuer to pay the interest rates on the bond and its nominal value within the time limits set by the issuer. There is no risk of default on municipal bonds as states and municipalities can raise taxes to pay off debt obligations. The bond market provides information on the level of default risk by publishing a rating of corporate and municipal bonds in terms of the position of default probability of two major agencies - Moody's Investors Service and Standard and Poor's. The bonds with a rating of Baa (or BBB) and above are considered securities graded as investments. Bonds with a rating lower than Baa (or BBB) are characterized by a higher risk of default and are called speculative or worthless bonds (junk bonds). In particular, if

we explain the ratio between interest rates on corporate and municipal bonds, first, because of the high risk of default, interest rates on corporate bonds are often higher than the interest rates on municipal bonds since the interest rate on Baa - rated bonds is higher than for Aaa-rated bonds with a higher credit rating. For this reason, states have various categories of credit ratings of one or another rating agency. As of January 1, 2018, the probability of default risk on municipal bonds issued by state and local governments in the United States is very low, and almost all municipal issuers have an investment grade rating. In particular, 92 percent of issued municipal bonds received a rating of Aaa or higher assigned by the rating agency Mood's (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Rating of municipal and corporate bonds¹

Insurance of municipal bonds represents a guarantee of monolithic insurance companies, in which the holders of municipal bonds receive interest and principal accrued over a specified period, even if its issuer is under default. Municipal bond

¹<https://www.invesco.com/us-rest/contentdetail?contentId=96ca582c5ed1d510VgnVCM100000c2f1bf0aRCRD&d>.

insurance is often considered as an increase in creditworthiness because it enables the municipality to borrow efficiently using the credit rating of an insurer that is higher, than its own rating.

5. Conclusion and proposals

In reliance upon the research results it can be concluded, that tax incentives on municipal bonds enable the state and local governments to reconsider the reasons for reducing borrowing costs: they raise the number of auction participants and encourage competitive bidding between existing bidders, which facilitates reduction of interest rates on bonds. This means that in the process of working out the policy aimed at developing the municipal bond market, it is required to reconsider the role of tax incentives, as well as other instruments directly related to the limited competition for these bonds in the primary market.

When determining the term of borrowing, the public administration authorities should take into consideration the forecast of budget parameters for the period within which the debt is expected to be repaid, as well as the schedule of repayment of debt obligations so that payments are not sharply higher in the short term.

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